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Recycling of SBS Modified Bitumen with Polymer Network Reconstructive Rejuvenators

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Concept: Reconstructive Rejuvenation

SBS modified bitumen aging

Concept: Reconstructive Rejuvenation

Concept: Reconstructive Rejuvenation

Chemo-physical rejuvenator

■ Benefits?

- Bitumen softening, polymer phase replenishment, and chemical chain reconnection at the same time.

Materials & Aging Procedure

- **SBS modified bitumen from TotalEnergies:**
 - 4PAV aging to simulate long-term aging in porous asphalt mixtures.
- **Ingredients for rejuvenators:**

Type	Code	Name
Oil	Aro	Aromatic oil
Oil	Rap	Rapeseed oil
Oil	Tall	Tall oil
SBS polymer	SBS	Kraton D1101 Linear SBS, supplied as powder
Chain extender	MDI	BASF IsoPMDI (Isocyanic acid, polymethylenepolyphenylene)

Test Framework Overview

Rheological Properties

- G^* & δ master curves
- MSCRT
- LAS
- Relaxation

Chemical Properties

Morphological Properties

Fluorescence microscopy

ESEM

Mastic Rheology

MSCRT...

Compatibility and Durability

Re-aging

Bleeding test

Adhesion and Ravelling

Pull-off test

Cantabro test

Mixture Validation

Cracking resistance

Moisture resistance

FTIR Insights: What Changes Chemically?

- **Oils:** dilute polymer signatures without restoring the SBS signal
- **Oil-SBS blends:** same SBS content but different response in FTIR
- **MDI only:** restores polymer index to unaged level
- **Chemo-physical:** enhance polymer incorporation beyond individual components
- FTIR confirms effective polymer restoration by chemical reconnection

DSR Master Curve Insights

- **Oils:** soften the binder but do not restore polymer response
- **Oil-SBS blends:** slightly increase stiffness and show limited polymer recovery
- **MDI only:** restores elasticity but at the cost of low-T
- **Chemo-physical:** balanced performance with great polymer response

MSCRT at 70 °C

- **Oils:** weak elasticity
- **Oil-SBS:** slight reinforcement
- **MDI only:** high elastic recovery exceeding the unaged binder
- **Chemo-physical:** closest balance to unaged binder – extra 0,5% MDI can already significantly improve elastic recovery

Creep-relaxation at 0 °C

- **Oils:** good low-temperature flexibility, low strength
- **Oil-SBS:** slightly higher values than pure oil
- **MDI only:** stiff and brittle
- **Chemo-physical:** balanced elasticity and relaxation, intermediate values, close to unaged binder.

Linear Amplitude Sweep / Fatigue Lifes

- **Oils:** fatigue life improve at large strains, but decrease at small strains
- **Oil-SBS:** better small-strain fatigue life than pure oil
- **MDI only:** highest small-strain capacity but brittle at high strain
- **Chemo-physical:** balanced excessive stiffness, consistently higher fatigue life than aged binder

Microstructure Evidence (FL + ESEM)

- **Oils:** reintroduce fibrillar structures but no help on polymers
- **Oil-SBS blends:** form polymer-rich bubbles
- **MDI only:** produces larger, denser domains indicating renewed bonding
- **Chemo-physical:** fine, well-distributed polymer structures indicative of effective network reconstruction

A short summary and what next?

Rejuvenator Type	Bitumen Softening	Polymer Restoration	Elasticity	Relaxation	Fatigue
Oil	✓✓	X	X	✓✓	△
Oil-SBS Blend	✓	△	△	△	△
Chemical Connector	X	✓✓	✓✓	X	X
Chemo-physical System	✓	✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓

- Any room in recipes adjusting for extra performance improvement?
- How about in a realistic scenario (50% aged binder recycling)?

4. Optimizing and 50% recycling validation

- Elastic recovery increases as MDI content increases.
- By having 18% tall oil-SBS blend + 2% MDI, the elastic recovery can match the unaged level.
- 50% aged + 50% fresh blend can already improve elastic response a lot.
- Pure oil, oil-SBS blend only reduces the elasticity.
- Chemo-physical rejuvenator further increase elastic recovery.

4. Optimizing and 50% recycling validation

- Effects at mastic level become more pronounced.
- Chemo-physical rejuvenator can significantly improve elastic response, exceeding unaged level.

4. Optimizing and 50% recycling validation

- By having 18% tall oil-SBS blend + 2% MDI, the low temperature performance can match the unaged level.
- Extra chemo-physical rejuvenator to the blends can extra improve performance.

4. Optimizing and 50% recycling validation

- Effects at mastic level become more pronounced.
- Extra chemo-physical rejuvenator to the blends can extra improve performance.

5. Conclusion (based on the whole project)

- Explored **reaction mechanism** of chemical compound and proved it can repair degraded SBS polymers, found out **adding sequence** to maximize rejuvenation effects.
- It is possible to use **all three rejuvenation components**: oil, polymer, and reactive chemical connector, and found out the one could **balance those three components and achieve maximum rejuvenation effects**.
- The best-performing rejuvenator is capable of restoring the **rejuvenated bitumen to the same performance level as its unaged counterpart**, in terms of high- and low-temperature properties and fatigue life.
- **Validated the rejuvenation effectiveness** at mastic and mixture's level.